

Some properties of a novel fractional Fourier transform

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ABSTRACT

Extension of Fourier transform gained substantial attention of scientific community since last four decades. Various methods of fractionalization of Fourier transform from different approaches are available on the basis of its diverse applications. Every novel fractional Fourier transform has its own algebra and operational calculus. This paper deals with some identities of a newly introduced Fourier transform of fractional order. been derived analytically in the environment of fractional calculus. Some properties including Product theorem and Parseval's identity have been derived analytically in the environment of fractional calculus. Results produced in the article may be applicable to engender the application of FrFT in various sectors of science and engineering.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fourier transform started as a numerical technique to solve problems of diverse disciplines in the early of 18th century. But it acquired huge attention of mathematician and engineers in the 19th century. Scientists of vivid sectors hugely applied it as a mathematical tool [1-3]. It played the most significant role in the development of signal processing and signal analysis [4-6]. Although it was recognized as the most extensively used mathematical tool in the field of electronics, communication and

electrical engineering, but it is extended due to its limitations in mobile communication, Quantum mechanics and some other fields [7-10].

Fractionalization of Fourier transform was presented by Wiener in 1929[11]. But it was consolidated by V. Namias in 1980 [12]. Massive remarkable work have been reported by scientists and engineers using the definition of FrFT given by Namias[13-19]. Digital computation of FrFT produced numerous applications [20]. FrFT is recognised as the most powerful and better tool as compare to the Fourier transform [21-38].

Subsequently various definition of FrFT have been reported using different approaches [39-44]. Recently Shukla et. al. presented a novel definition of FrFT using fractional derivative [45]. We have attempted to develop some of properties of this newly introduced FrFT. Including some basic properties we derived the Product theorem and Parseval's identity.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 [1] Let f be a function of class C, then its Fourier transform FT is defined as-

$$FT(f(t))=F(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\lambda}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\omega t} f(t)dt \quad (i)$$

Definition 2.2 [1] Let f be a function of class C, then its Inverse Fourier transform IFT is defined as-

$$IFT (F(\omega)) = f(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\lambda}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i\omega t} F(\omega)dt \quad (ii)$$

2.3 Fourier transform of derivative of $f(t)$ can be expressed as [1]

$$FT\left(\frac{d^n f}{dt^n}\right) = (-i\omega)^n F(\omega) \quad (iii)$$

Where function $f(t)$ and its nth order derivatives vanish at $\pm\infty$

We will use following identities [1]

[I] Fourier transform of fractional derivative

$$\text{FT}(D^a f(t)) = f_a(\omega) = (-i\omega)^a F(\omega) \quad (\text{iV})$$

[II] Fractional order integration of inverse Fourier transform

$$D^{-a} \text{IFT}(f_a(\omega)) = f(t)$$

2.4 Fourier transform of fractional order

Shukla et. al. [45] Presented following definition of Fourier transform of fractional order.

$$f_a(\omega) = (-i\omega)^a F(\omega) \quad (\text{V})$$

Where a is the fractional angle.

Following identities on newly introduced FrFT can be easily derive.

Theorem 1. First shifting theorem of fractional Fourier transform

If $f_a(\omega)$ is fractional Fourier transform of $f(t)$, then

$$f_a \{ e^{iat} f(t) \} = f_a \{ f(\omega - a) \}$$

Theorem 2. Second shifting theorem of fractional Fourier transform

If $f_a(\omega)$ is fractional Fourier transform of $f(t)$, then

$$f_a \{ f(t - a) \} = \{ e^{-i\omega a} f_a(\omega) \}$$

Theorem 3. Change of scale property of fractional Fourier transform

If $f_a(\omega)$ is fractional Fourier transform of $f(t)$, then

$$f_a \{ f(at) \} = 1/a f_a(\omega/a)$$

Now we will prove Parseval's identity of novel FrFT.

Parseval identity of Fourier transform is well known [1]

$$(I) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) * \bar{g}(t) dt = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(\omega) * \bar{G}(\omega) d\omega$$

$$(II) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f(t)|^2 dt = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [F(\omega)]^2 d\omega$$

Theorem 4. Parseval’s identity of fractional Fourier transform

We prove following Parseval’s identities for this newly defined transform

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) * \bar{g}(t) dt = \frac{1}{2\lambda} (-i\omega)^a \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_a(\omega) \bar{g}_a(\omega) d\omega \quad (vi)$$

Proof $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) * \bar{g}(t) dt = (-i\omega)^a \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) \left[\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \bar{g}_a(\omega) e^{-i\omega t} d\omega \right] dt$

using Inverse fractional Fourier transform

Where $f(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_a(\omega) e^{i\omega t} d\omega$

$$= (-i\omega)^a \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \bar{g}_a(\omega) \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt \right] d\omega$$

$$= (-i\omega)^a \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \bar{g}_a(\omega) f_a(\omega) d\omega$$

When $f(t) = g(t)$ then $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f(t)|^2 dt = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [f_a(\omega)]^2 d\omega$

Theorem 5. Product theorem for fractional Fourier transform

We establish following Product theorem for newly defined fractional Fourier transform.

If $f(t)$ and $g(t)$ are two function of class C then FrFT of

$$\{f(t). g(t)\}(\omega) = \frac{1}{2\lambda} [f_a(\omega) * g_a(\omega)] \quad (Vii)$$

Proof If $f(t)$ and $g(t)$ are two continuous functions and $h(t) = f(t). g(t)$. Then fractional Fourier transform of Product is explained as-

$$h_a(\omega) = D^{-\alpha} \frac{1}{2\bar{\lambda}} (f_a(\omega) * g_a(\omega))$$

Proof Let $h(t) = f(t) \cdot g(t)$

Then its fractional order Fourier transform

$$h_a(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) g(t) e^{-i\omega t} (-i\omega)^a dt$$

now, write $f(t)$ in its inverse transform

$$f(t) = D^{-\alpha} (IFT(FT D^{\alpha} f(t)))$$

$$f(t) = D^{-\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{2\bar{\lambda}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} FT(D^{\alpha} f(t)) e^{iut} du \right)$$

$$\text{Then } h_a(\omega) = (-i\omega)^a \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) g(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt$$

$$= D^{-\alpha} \frac{(-i\omega)^a}{2\bar{\lambda}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (FT D^{\alpha} f(t)) e^{iut} g(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt du$$

$$= D^{-\alpha} \frac{(-i\omega)^a}{2\bar{\lambda}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (FT D^{\alpha} f(t)) e^{iut} \cdot e^{-i\omega t} g(t) dt du$$

$$= D^{-\alpha} \frac{(-i\omega)^a}{2\bar{\lambda}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (f_a(\omega) e^{i(u-\omega)t} g(t) dt) du$$

$$= D^{-\alpha} \frac{1}{2\bar{\lambda}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (f_a(\omega) g_a(u - \omega)) du$$

$$= D^{-\alpha} \frac{1}{2\bar{\lambda}} (f_a(\omega) * g_a(\omega)) \quad \text{By Convolution Theorem}$$

3. CONCLUSION

Fractionalization of the transform using fractional derivatives is a novel area of interest. This article studied some significant properties of a newly defined fractional Fourier transform in the environment of fractional calculus. Paper presented Product theorem and Parseval's identity

including some basic properties. These results may be very useful in numerous field of science and engineering.

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